

Maturity checklist v0.5

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Introduction

This maturity checklist is designed to enable GLAM and HASS organisations to assess their AI evaluation maturity. The checklist uses the H-STRICT principles as a guiding framework and invites practitioners to self-assess their organisation's maturity against each principle.

Through the exercise of completing the maturity checklist, organisations can reflect on their current AI evaluation maturity and develop plans for deepening their expertise, building their AI evaluation infrastructure, and expanding the scope of their responsible AI decision making.

Maturity levels

Maturity levels based on Microsoft's Responsible AI maturity model (Vorvoreanu et al. 2023). Responsible decision-making scope levels based on the Library of Congress LC Labs' AI framework (Manchester 2023; Manchester et al. 2024).

	Maturity level		
Responsible decision-making scope What sort of AI decisions is your organisation set up to make well?	Latent Your organisation has a general interest in AI use, but no routinised processes for AI decision making.	Developing Your organisation has started to develop some AI decision making capacity but is still in a learning phase.	Leading Your organisation has robust, routinised, and accountable processes for AI decision making.
Understand Responsible decision-making focuses on setting high-level guardrails for AI use, and charting a path towards greater AI capacity	<i>Decide on guiding principles to inform AI use</i> <i>Decide on priority use cases for evaluation and who will be responsible for evaluation</i>		

	<p><i>Decide</i> on priority areas for expertise and policy development</p> <p>Begin in-house, low-cost, guard-railed trials of AI tools in defined areas to inform evaluation design.</p>		
<p>Experiment Responsible decision-making focuses on design of AI evaluations, ensuring alignment with organizational values and processes.</p>		<p><i>Decide</i> on how guiding principles will be implemented in AI evaluations <i>Decide</i> on AI evaluation design for priority use cases, including benchmarks for AI deployment <i>Decide</i> on evaluation partners and tools for priority use cases</p> <p>Begin in-house or externally supported evaluation of priority AI use cases.</p>	
<p>Implement Responsible decision-making focuses on embedding AI evaluation practices in the organisation, and on process of moving from AI evaluation to deployment</p>			<p><i>Decide</i> on scaling process for successful AI evaluations <i>Decide</i> on standard evaluation practices, templates, and processes <i>Decide</i> on processes for ensuring evaluation practices stay up to date</p>

			<p><i>Decide on design and development of in-house evaluation tools</i></p> <p>Begin organisation-wide deployment of successfully evaluated AI use cases.</p>
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Checklist

	Maturity level			
	<p>Latent Your organisation has a general interest in AI use, but no routinised processes for AI decision making.</p> <p><i>Begin in-house, low-cost, guard-railed trials of AI tools in defined areas, to inform evaluation design.</i></p>	<p>Developing Your organisation has started to develop some AI decision making capacity but is still in a learning phase.</p> <p><i>Begin in-house or externally supported evaluation of priority AI use cases.</i></p>	<p>Leading Your organisation has robust, routinised, and accountable processes for AI decision making.</p> <p><i>Begin organisation-wide deployment of successfully evaluated AI use cases.</i></p>	
<p>Principle</p> <p>Human The values, ethics, and standards applied during the evaluation of an AI system should reflect the expectations and commitments of the</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Our organisation has a general purpose Statement of Values or similar document, declaring the values that guide our technology use</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Our Statement of Values has been used to</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Within our organisation, it is clear who is responsible for ensuring alignment between AI use and our Statement of values</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Our organisation has specific policies</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Our organisation has a formal consultation process for incorporating AI experts and community perspectives in AI decision making</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Within our organisation, there is</p>	<p>Key artefacts or tools</p> <p>Statement of values or similar statement of ethical principles (e.g. Cordell 2020; Government Chief Digital Officer 2024)</p>

<p>humans who will develop, use, interact with, and be impacted by the AI system.</p>	<p>develop practical guidelines for staff on AI use <input type="checkbox"/> Our organisation has conducted introductory training on AI, its use and risks, for relevant staff</p>	<p>informing how Indigenous data or knowledge may / may not be used in AI systems</p>	<p>dedicated resourcing and expertise directed towards monitoring and managing AI use</p>	<p>Guidelines for implementing ethical principles within the organisation (e.g. guidelines for implementing Australia’s Ethical AI principles: CSIRO and Gradient Institute 2023; guidelines for AI use in parliaments: Fitsilis, Lucke, and Vrieze 2024)</p> <p>AI training resources for the GLAM sector overview (Darby et al. 2022)</p> <p>9/26/2025 12:21:00 AM</p>
<p>System targets When conceptualising how to evaluate an AI system, the scope of the evaluation should extend -- i.e. target -- to the full breadth of sociotechnical components implicated in an AI system, rather than</p>		<p><input type="checkbox"/> Our organisation maintains a well-documented dataset for use in AI evaluations <input type="checkbox"/> Our organisation maintains access to well-documented models for use in AI evaluations <input type="checkbox"/> Our organisation has evaluated and selected preferred suppliers for off-the-shelf AI tools</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Our organisation has an established process for mapping and documenting all AI system components <input type="checkbox"/> Our organisation has an evaluation platform that enables different AI system components to be combined and compared during evaluations</p>	<p>Checklist for publishing collections data (Candela et al. 2025; Lee 2025)</p>

<p>only to the AI models themselves.</p>			<input type="checkbox"/> Our organisation has evaluated and selected preferred suppliers for custom-built AI tools <input type="checkbox"/> Our organisation has clear policies in place for appropriate use of off-the-shelf AI tools	
<p>Transparent The various points of calibration for the system target (e.g. model settings, interface settings) should be transparently recorded during an evaluation and exposed to evaluation participants.</p>		<input type="checkbox"/> Our organisation has template evaluation plans, which include sections for recording system target settings <input type="checkbox"/> Our organisation shares evaluation findings informally with peer organisations	<input type="checkbox"/> Our organisation has adopted a standard approach to documenting and recording all aspects of AI technologies that we use (e.g. model card, data card, evaluation card) <input type="checkbox"/> Our organisation maintains a publicly accessible register of AI evaluations and AI uses	<p>Data processing plan (part of the LC Labs AI framework (Manchester et al. 2024))</p> <p>Data and model cards (Alkemade et al. 2023; Gebru et al. 2021; Mitchell et al. 2019; Pushkarna, Zaldivar, and Kjartansson 2022))</p> <p>Use case cards, which can be adapted to include all evaluation settings (Hupont et al. 2024) and the CLeAR documentation framework, which can guide adaption (Chmielinski et al. 2024)</p>

<p>Reproducible The probabilistic process by which AI models produce outputs, coupled with the unpredictable ways these outputs may interact with other system components, needs to be accounted for during evaluation.</p>		<p><input type="checkbox"/> Our organisation has template evaluation plans, which include sections describing how an evaluation was conducted and can be repeated</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Our organisation has a basic process in place for documenting evaluation plans and outcomes, including tracking what data, models, and so on are used</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Our organisation has a routine process for reviewing and revisiting AI evaluations</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Our organisation has a technology platform that enables routine re-running of AI evaluations</p>	<p>Example technology framework for reproducible AI evaluations (UK AI Safety Institute n.d.)</p>
<p>Iterative AI systems should be treated as dynamic, with an expectation of changing performance over time. Accordingly, evaluation approaches should be iterative, focused on establishing baselines and then monitoring performance over time.</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Our organisation has put in place a basic knowledge base (e.g. Wiki), to enable early lessons and experimental results to be recorded</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Our organisation has a basic process in place for reporting emerging issues</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Our organisation has an ongoing training program, to ensure our AI knowledge base is kept up to date</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Our organisation has established AI guidelines for staff designing or participating in evaluations</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Our organisation has in-house expertise in AI development and use, enabling us to update evaluation approaches as needed</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Our organisation has established processes for reviewing and updating AI guidelines for staff, based on emerging lessons</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Our organisation has routine ways of monitoring AI performance, with clear processes in place for</p>	<p>Data management plan, for recording and managing evaluation data (e.g. the data management plan in The Turing Way Community 2022)</p> <p>While not directly applicable, see Padilla (2019) for detailed description of working groups and learning structures that can support AI engagement</p>

			how to respond to performance declines or emerging issues	
<p>Contextually Informed Measures & Baselines</p> <p>AI systems ought to be designed and deployed in ways that account for local context. A primary goal of an AI evaluation is to determine alignment between an AI system and its deployment context.</p>	<input type="checkbox"/> Our organisation has a basic understanding of common AI risks (hallucinations, biased outputs) and use cases identified for early testing have been assessed against these risks	<input type="checkbox"/> Our organisation has identified priority risks against which all AI use cases need to be evaluated <input type="checkbox"/> Our organisation has clear benchmarks (e.g. in terms of sustainability, user feedback, return-on-investment) defined for success in an AI evaluation	<input type="checkbox"/> Our organisation has established processes for monitoring and reporting on AI use, risks, and harms, with clear accountability processes for addressing any detected harms <input type="checkbox"/> Our organisation has developed bespoke performance benchmarks for AI systems, based on our unique local context	<p>Phase II use case risk worksheet, covering success criteria and risk/benefit analysis (part of the LC Labs AI framework (Manchester et al. 2024))</p> <p>For example high-level framework for establishing and monitoring measures see NIST Risk Management Framework (Tabassi 2023)</p>
<p>Tasks, workflows & use cases</p> <p>Although AI systems are frequently marketed as general purpose tools, evaluations need to be undertaken at the level of specific tasks, workflows, and use cases, as good performance in one</p>	<input type="checkbox"/> Our organisation has undertaken a prioritization exercise, and determined a shortlist of priority use cases for evaluation <input type="checkbox"/> Our organisation has identified high-risk use cases that ought to be avoided until AI maturity has deepened	<input type="checkbox"/> Our organisation has a standard approach to soliciting ideas for potential use cases and for assessing their risks <input type="checkbox"/> Our organisation has a standard approach for eliciting use case requirements, including consultation with potential AI users	<input type="checkbox"/> Our organisation has a knowledge library established, to track and record potential AI use cases, their risk assessment, and evaluation status <input type="checkbox"/> Our organisation has clear accountability processes for instances where AI is used without appropriate evaluation	<p>Use case risk worksheet (part of the LC Labs AI framework (Manchester et al. 2024))</p> <p>Collection of open source tools and AI use cases, for museums (Mazzanti et al. 2025)</p> <p>Example of analysis of priority use cases and</p>

<p>domain or use case should not be assumed to be predictive of good performance in another.</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Our organisation has clear policies on how organizational data can/cannot be used with commercial AI products (e.g. ChatGPT)</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Our organisation has identified low-risk data/collections that can be used in early AI evaluations</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Our organisation has standardized approaches to user testing, with clear acceptance criteria</p>	<p>approach to evaluation (National Library of Australia 2025)</p> <p>Example of a policy outlining data use with AI technologies (The National Archives 2024)9/26/2025 12:21:00 AM</p>
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Sources

Checklist prompts and artefacts have been gathered through review of AI evaluation frameworks and guidelines, listed below.

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